

WORLD EXPERIENCE IN PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP PROJECTS

Khusanova Dilrabakhon Botiraliyevna

independent researcher of the Institute for retraining and professional development of directors and specialists of pre-school educational organizations

TAFU, Head of the Department of Preschool Education Methodology,
Associate Professor **X.I.Yusupova**

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Abstract: In this article, public-private partnership relations in the preschool education system of foreign countries in public-private partnership projects information about.

Keywords: public-private partnership, comprehensive, systematic, concept, didactic, voucher and concession.

Public-private partnerships are well established in the preschool education system of foreign countries. For example, in the preschool education system in Kazakhstan, in recent years, the private sector and public-private partnership relations have been given a lot of attention. In this process, children's coverage of preschool education increased significantly due to the introduction of financing for each pupil, the abolition of compulsory licenses for activities in this sector, the introduction of sanitary-hygiene requirements for preschool educational organizations and relaxation of building codes.

In the USA, non-governmental preschool organizations established on the basis of public-private partnership are given significant financial and material support by municipalities and parents. Subsidies are allocated for the care of the children of the low-income families covered by this type of pre-school education organizations, and the costs for the rest of the children are covered by the parents.

Privileges such as allotment of free land for establishment of non-governmental preschool education organizations on the basis of public-private partnership in Pakistan, concessions for electricity and gas consumption, exemption from taxes and income tax on import of certain listed goods from abroad. Also, in some states of Pakistan, citizens are provided monthly non-refundable money (voucher) for education at the expense of various funds.

In some regions of the Russian Federation, various public-private partnerships are being tested in order to increase the enrollment of children in preschool educational institutions. In particular, experiences such as issuing vouchers giving the right to free education for low-income families with many children, allocating targeted subsidies, and organizing preschool education organizations in households were carried out. The concept of public-private partnership has been given different definitions by different countries.

For example, in the USA, public-private partnership is understood as an agreement between state and private enterprises that allows participation in the state's property. Such an agreement implies that a contract has been signed between a representative of the state and a representative of a private enterprise, and the subject of the contract is the

reconstruction, construction and/or current repair, management, etc. of the object belonging to the state.

European Union countries define public-private partnership as follows. For example, in Great Britain, public-private partnerships are widespread, and public-private partnerships are seen as a key element in providing high-quality and competitive public services.

Public-private partnerships have a rich history. The first construction of a canal in France under a concession agreement dates back to 1552. In Britain in the 17th and 18th centuries, the famous East India Company, which was involved in the management of India and other colonies, was given state benefits - a concession. At the end of the 19th and 20th centuries, during the period of rapid construction, the development of railways and the steel industry, the model of concession contract was actively used in many countries. The Eiffel Tower was built under such a contract.

Later, in post-war Europe, various forms of public-private partnerships began to be used to restore local infrastructure.

To date, the European Union countries have the most developed regulatory and practical framework for regulating public-private partnerships, which is already widespread.

In the works of Russian scientists VGVarnavsky, AVKlimenko, VAKorolev, the formation of the system of economic relations between the state and the private sector, the economic nature and content of the category "public-private partnership", goals and objectives, structure and models, the main directions of economic activity between state and private business entities, state and sources of financial resources for the implementation of forms of cooperation between entrepreneurship, directions related to state and public property objects were studied.

Directive 2004/18/YEC and 2004/17/YEC on the management of public-private partnership projects have been adopted across Europe. "Green Book of Public-Private Partnership" is the only methodological framework in the field of public-private sector within the European Union.

In international practice, there are significant financial mechanisms, on the basis of which public-private partnership projects are put into practice. The most important of these mechanisms are:

- 1) budget resources of different levels;
- 2) funds of state enterprises, organizations and institutions;
- 3) funds of the private sector;
- 4) funds of public and non-commercial structures;
- 5) credit resources of financial organizations and credit institutions;
- 6) issuance of securities;
- 7) funds of foreign countries and private investors;
- 8) funds at the disposal of individuals, etc

In global practice, public-private partnership mechanisms are widely used to attract private companies for the purpose of long-term financing and management of public infrastructure.

The most important aspect of public-private partnership projects in the social sphere is that they should be launched and implemented on time, not in the distant future. **There is a constant need for the social sector. It is necessary to** modernize the existing ones and build new infrastructures. This is typical of both developing and developed countries.

Public-private partnership projects can be implemented in many sectors and fields, and the choice of the primary areas of its implementation is decided independently based on the level of socio-economic development and policy of the state. In our country, public-private partnership is rapidly developing in the social sphere.

Different types, forms and areas of use of public-private partnership projects make them a universal mechanism for solving various types of long-term problems.

The UK was one of the first countries to legislate public-private partnerships. The first step for this was the adoption of a special concept called "Private Finance Initiative (PFI)" in 1992. Its meaning was to give private companies the functions of construction, reconstruction and use of state-owned social infrastructure objects.

three stages of development of public-private partnership projects in the world . Many countries are still in the early stages of public-private partnership development. That is, they are in the process of developing standards and legal documents for public-private partnership. Countries that have started to introduce public-private partnerships can use the experience gained by countries that have passed this stage.

Currently, only Great Britain, Australia and Ireland are in the third stage of public-private partnership .

most of the developed countries of Europe (France , Spain , Italy, Greece , Germany), USA, Canada, Japan and New Zealanders are included .

Eastern European countries, Latin American countries , Russian and CIS countries are included in the first stage of development .

It is surprising that in developed countries such as Great Britain , Turkey, Holland, USA, Canada, China, there is no legal framework for public-private partnership.

In Great Britain, the importance of the public-private partnership system does not exist in practice regarding the restriction of the activities of the state or competent authorities in the matters of concluding relevant contracts. 1997 for municipalities In 2015, the Law "On Contracts for Local Authorities" was adopted, giving them the right to directly implement public-private partnership projects. It is for this reason that public institutions and private companies use model projects developed by the competent departments of the Ministry of Finance, which respond to the system of public-private partnerships of Great Britain and other specialized institutions.

Public-private partnership projects have specific sector priorities of different countries :

According to international experience, one of the main mechanisms of effective management of state property and economic development in the last decade is public-private partnership. Such cooperation is a new phenomenon in the world economy.

In the world economy, there are a number of factors that influence the expansion of the scope and forms of relations between the state and business:

1. Public-private partnership is one of the mechanisms of the mixed economy, which involves the development of mutual relations between the state and business.

2. Public-private partnership involves the involvement of entrepreneurs' resources in the production processes in sectors and industries owned by the state and local authorities.

3. Uniting the power and resources of the state and business within specific projects is their additional competitive advantage. Compared to state institutions, private entrepreneurship has a desire for technical and technological improvement, assimilation of

innovations, speed of decision-making, and high mobility to ensure competitiveness. The correct and effective creation of the legal framework of the sector in the state ensures the successful implementation of public-private partnership projects.

In conclusion: In general, public-private partnership is understood in two ways in world practice. First, the system of public and private sector cooperation is widely used as a means of national, global, regional, economic and social development. Secondly, specific projects are implemented for state-owned objects based on the joint activities of state bodies and private companies. Also, the main goal of the public-private partnership is to increase the efficiency of social infrastructure organizations and ensure a regular increase in the standard of living of the population in the society. It is very difficult to do this without the participation of public and private companies. The key performance indicators of private companies are efficiency and profitability.

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